

Causes and Social Consequences of Cultism Among Students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo State: Implications for School Counselling

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Abstract

This study examined the causes and social consequences of cultism among students of The Polytechnic, Ibadan, Oyo State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. A sample of 240 respondents was used, and data were obtained through a structured instrument titled Causes and Social Consequences of Cultism Questionnaire (CSCCQ). Five experts from the Department of Mass Communication at The Polytechnic, Ibadan, validated the content of the instrument. The reliability of the questionnaire was determined using the test–retest method, which yielded a coefficient of 0.84. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive and inferential statistical methods. The findings indicated that peer group pressure, inadequate guidance and counselling services, and negative media exposure were the major causes of cultism. The study revealed that cultism leads to grave social consequences, such as the untimely death of innocent students, life imprisonment, and damage to personal reputation. The results showed no significant differences in the causes and social consequences of cultism among respondents based on gender. Therefore, it was recommended that students should be empowered by school counsellors, lecturers, and parents through life skills training, mentorship, and counselling to resist negative peer pressure that can lead to cultism while fostering a supportive and inclusive environment. School management should educate students through orientation programmes or seminars about the dangers of cultism and its social consequences, including untimely death of innocent students, life imprisonment, character assassination, and disruption of school's academic calendar, to prevent its spread on campus.

Keywords: Causes, Social consequences, Cultism, Students, Ibadan Polytechnic, Oyo State

Introduction

Education equips youths with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to become responsible and socially conscious citizens. In tertiary institutions, including universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education, participation in campus clubs and organisations help students develop leadership, social, and interpersonal skills, shaping them into well-rounded and disciplined individuals by the time they complete their studies. This engagement not only fosters personal growth and moral development but also promotes teamwork, constructive interaction, and academic excellence within the campus community. The positive and nurturing environment in Nigerian higher education institutions remained intact until about five decades ago, when the rise of cultism disrupted campus life, introducing violence, fear, and social instability, and undermining the developmental and educational goals of these institutions.

Cultism in Nigeria is broadly categorised into two types; namely, traditional cults and institutional cults (also known as confraternities or campus cults). Traditional cults have roots in indigenous belief systems and secret societies and these include the Aborigine Ogboni Fraternity, Oshugbo Guild, Shapona, Eyibi/Eluku, Gelede, Olokun, Agemo and a host of others (Ugwu & Chukwuma, 2021; Omenu, 2025). Institutional cults began as fraternities within universities with the initial aim of maintaining order. Over time, some of these societies, such as the Pyrates Confraternity, Buccaneers Confraternity, Black Axe, Vikings, Eiyé (a Yoruba name for bird), Black Queens, and Daughters of Jezebel, have become more involved in violence and power struggles, and many tertiary institutions are gradually becoming breeding grounds for armed robbers, arsonists, rapists, political thugs, and perpetrators of all forms of criminal activities (Iheanacho et al., 2023; Nwikpo, et al., 2025).

Cultism in Nigerian tertiary institutions began in 1952 when Professor Wole Soyinka, the 1986 Nobel Laureate in Literature, together with six colleagues, established the Pyrates Confraternity Elite at the University College Ibadan (now University of Ibadan), which was then affiliated with the University of London (Adedeji, 2022; Aroyehun, 2024). The organisation was formed to maintain law and order on campus and to develop future Nigerian leaders who would take pride in their African heritage. Also referred to as the National Association of Sea Dogs and guided by the motto “Against all moribund conventions,” the Pyrates Confraternity sought to oppose foreign customs through intellectual and non-violent methods, revive the ideals of chivalry, and tackle issues of tribalism and elitism (Ugwu & Chukwuma, 2021; Adegoke, 2022). **Subsequent to the Pyrates**, the Supreme Eiyé Confraternity was founded in 1958 and later became the National Association of Airlords (NAA) in 1963 at the University of Ibadan, making it the second oldest confraternity in Nigeria (Ogunleke, 2025).

Some cults, although originally founded with positive objectives, eventually became instruments of intimidation, victimisation, sexual abuse, and extortion, often under political influence. The development of campus cults in Nigerian tertiary institutions began separating from the Pyrates Confraternity in 1970. Hence, in 1972, Bolaji Carew and several others were expelled from the Pyrates for failing to meet the organisation’s standards (Olayiwola et al., 2023; Fajemirokun, 2025), which led the Pyrates to formally register as the National Association of Seadogs (NAS). Following his expulsion, Bolaji Carew later founded the Buccaneers of Seadogs. The Supreme Vikings Confraternity, also known as the National Association of Adventurers or the De Norsemen Klub International (DNKI), was founded in 1982 by three former Buccaneers members at the University of Port Harcourt. The Neo-Black Movement of Africa (Black Axe) emerged from the University of Benin, Edo State, in 1976 (Ernest & Okeke, 2025), followed by the Green Circuit Association International (Maphite) in May 1978, also at the University of Benin.

The Mafia Confraternity, commonly known as the Family Fraternity or Ciao Sons, is a notable cult group in Nigeria. It was founded in 1978 at the University of Ilorin (UNILORIN) and subsequently began active operations at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, in 1980, following its establishment by eight students. Another infamous confraternity, the Brotherhood of the Blood—also known as Two-Two or Black Beret—was established at the Enugu State University of Science and Technology (Adedeji, 2022). The Victor Charlie Boys was formed by Augustine Ahiazu while serving as vice-chancellor of the Rivers State University of Science and Technology (Fayokun, 2025). In the early 1990s, a number of other cults were founded, including Night Cadet, Thu-Thu, Sonmen, Mgba Mgba Brothers, Temple of Eden, Trojan Horse, Jurists, White Bishops,

Gentlemen Clubs, Fame, Executioners, Dreaded Friends of Friends, Eagle Club, Black Scorpion, Red Sea Horse, and the Fraternity of Friends (Adegoke, 2022).

The Dedy Na Debt, also called the Eternal Fraternal Order of Legion Consortium or Klansmen Konfraternity, was founded in 1983 by five students at the University of Calabar. The group expanded its influence by establishing a street and creek faction known as Deebam, which engaged in violent activities to assert control over territories beyond the university campuses. In response, the Supreme Vikings Confraternity (SVC) created its own street and creek unit, Dewell. When Dewell proved unable to match Deebam, the SVC formed a second wing, the Icelanders (German), under the leadership of militia commander Ateke Tom. Numerous other street and creek confraternities, collectively referred to as the Outlaws, also emerged. These include groups such as Black Bra, Black Berets, Pink Ladies, White Angels, Temple of Eden Vampires, the Viqueens, Daughters of Jezebel, The Ten Wonderful Girls, White Ladies, Sisters of Darkness, The Royal Queens, The Knights of the Aristos, and The Damsel, among others (Fayokun, 2025). University authorities classify these organisations as secret cults because they operate outside the law and impose their own form of justice (Jumbo et al., 2021).

The problem of cultism has led to the deaths of many innocent individuals, including students, lecturers, and senior officials in higher education institutions (Adegoke, 2022). Nigerian institutions are swimming in the ocean of cult activities perpetrated by students, and Polytechnic of Ibadan is also sharing in the tales of woes resulting from these activities as effective teaching, learning and general administration of the institution have been disrupted severally. The situation has become a great eyesore which must be attended to without delay since the future of this nation depends on youths who are swimming in the hands of the devil, the arch-enemy of man (Adedeji, 2022). For instance, in 2022, Nigerian police arrested students of Polytechnic Ibadan for terrorising different places in Ibadan over the acts of violence, harassment, robbery, kidnapping, ritualism, and cultism. Dangerous items recovered from these students were 14 ammunition, two cutlasses, two arms, voodoo, one sledge hammer, hard drugs among others (Folorunsho, 2025).

Ogunleke (2025) reported that more than 26,789 deaths were reported between 2008 and 2023 due to cult clashes on Nigerian campuses, while 581 reported in 2024 alone. The situation is highly pathetic, and this cancerous problem has consistently defiled the multi-dimensional steps taken by the school authority and the government to avert it. Most students who join cults are between 18 and 30 years old, doing so either by choice, financial assistance, peer pressure, manipulation, or vulnerability to persuasive recruitment tactics. Strategies used to recruit new members include cajoling, setups, talent hunting, and intimidation (Yabagi & Okau, 2025). This is evident in their involvement in criminal acts, rituals, holding of secret meetings, and addressing political issues both within and outside the campus setup. They are involved in all kinds of prohibited activities on campus, such as ceremonial sacrifices, causing disputes among students, and raping female students (Aroyehun, 2024).

Hence, the causes of cultism among students are multifaceted, including peer pressure, poor parental upbringing, negative peer influence, societal decadence, declining educational standards, and the militarisation of the Nigerian polity, the quest for power, and unresolved grievances within the school system. Many students, especially those who feel marginalised or insecure, are lured into cult groups with promises of influence, protection, and belonging (Adedeji, 2022). Peer pressure is significant, as students often join to gain acceptance or avoid intimidation. Inadequate

parental guidance and poor moral upbringing also leave youths vulnerable to cult recruitment (Fayokun, 2025). Furthermore, the failure of school authorities to address injustice, victimisation, and indiscipline encourages cultism among both genders (Ugwu & Chukwuma, 2021). Exposure to violent media, poverty, and the erosion of traditional values further worsen the problem, creating an environment where cultism appears attractive. Also, the glorification of violence and power in society can influence students to view cult groups as a pathway to status and relevance.

Statement of the Problem

The impact of cultism is wide-ranging, manifesting in school violence, student indiscipline, poor academic performance, psychological trauma, engagement in criminal activities, and, in extreme cases, loss of life. Cultism creates a climate of fear in schools, disrupts academic activities, and damages the moral and social development of students, regardless of gender (Iheanacho et al., 2023). Both male and female students are affected by the fear and tension created by cult-related violence, which disrupts the learning environment and makes it unsafe for students and staff alike. This hostile atmosphere can lead to a decline in educational standards and hinder the effective delivery of academic programmes in affected institutions (Adedeji, 2022). Beyond academics, cultism exposes students, both male and female, to various forms of violence, substance abuse, and criminal behaviour. Initiation rites and rival clashes have resulted in injuries, loss of lives, and long-term psychological trauma for victims and witnesses of both genders. Cult involvement also increases the likelihood of arrests, imprisonment, and a tarnished reputation, which can ruin future career prospects and personal relationships (Aroyehun, 2024). It fosters a cycle of fear, retaliation, and insecurity within campuses and neighboring communities, eroding the moral and social fabric of society across gender lines. Thus, the dangers and consequences of cultism, if left unchecked, will not only ruin and rubbish the educational fabric of the country, but plunge the nation in widespread insecurity and chaos.

Several studies have examined the nature of cultism both within and outside Oyo State, but their findings are not entirely consistent. For instance, Adedeji (2022) investigated the prevalence of cultism in Nigerian tertiary institutions in Lagos State and found that peer influence and societal moral decay were the major contributors to its prevalence. However, Adegoke (2022) examined the academic consequences of cultism among secondary school students in Ogbomosho North Local Government of Oyo State, finding that students involved in cult activities had lower grades, higher absenteeism, and reduced academic motivation compared to non-involved peers. Similarly, Fayokun (2025) examined campus cultism in Nigeria's higher education institutions and highlighted its broader effects, including loss of lives and property, disruption of academic activities, and unsafe campus environments. These differences show a lack of consensus regarding the specific causes and social consequences of cultism across different contexts. To address this gap and contribute to the literature, the present study specifically investigates the causes and social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo State, providing context-specific insights that previous studies have not explored.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of the study was to investigate the causes and social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic, Oyo state, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of this study were to:

1. identify the causes of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo state.

2. examine the social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo state.

Research Questions

1. What are the causes of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo state?
2. What are the social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo state?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the causes of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo State based on gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo State based on gender.

Methods

The study employed a descriptive survey research design to examine the causes and social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic, Oyo State. The population comprised all students of the institution, and 240 respondents were selected using a combination of sampling techniques. Four faculties, namely Business and Communication Studies, Engineering, Environmental Studies, and Science, were chosen through simple random sampling by ballot, and two departments from each faculty were purposively selected based on population size. From these departments, sixty students per faculty were randomly selected to participate. Data were collected using a researcher-designed instrument, the *Causes and Social Consequences of Cultism Questionnaire (CSCCQ)*, developed from the literature. Content validity was established by five experts from the Department of Mass Communication, Ibadan Polytechnic, while reliability was measured through a test–retest procedure conducted over a two-week interval with students from the Department of Mass Communication at Adeseun Ogundoyin Polytechnic, Eruwa, yielding a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.84. The instrument had three sections. Section A collected demographic information, Section B measured the causes of cultism, and Section C examined its social consequences. Sections B and C were designed using a four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). A mean score of 2.5 was used as the cut-off point; mean values of 2.5 and above indicated the causes and social consequences of cultism, while values below 2.5 were considered not significant.

Results

This section presents the analysis of the data obtained. A total of 240 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, and 216 were properly completed and returned, forming the dataset for the study. The study's hypotheses were tested using the t-test at a 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Mean and Rank Order of Causes of Cultism among Students of Ibadan Polytechnic, Oyo State

S/N	Cultism among students is caused by:	Mean	Rank
1	negative peer influence	3.94	1 st
10	inadequate guidance and counselling services	3.92	2 nd
3	negative media influence	3.90	3 rd
8	influence of drug abuse	3.88	4 th
6	deplorable school facilities	3.85	5 th
2	lack of school discipline	3.76	6 th
4	negative parental influence	3.64	7 th
5	lack of moral upbringing	3.62	8 th
7	quest for power and protection	3.56	9 th
9	unlimited desire for material wealth	3.43	10 th

Table 1 showed the mean scores and rank order of the causes of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic, Oyo State. All the items listed were identified as contributing factors, as their mean scores exceeded the mid-point value of 2.50, indicating that students acknowledged them as causes of cultism. Although several factors were reported, the three most influential were negative peer influence (mean = 3.94), inadequate guidance and counselling services (mean = 3.92), and negative media influence (mean = 3.90), which were ranked first, second, and third, respectively. This highlights that while multiple factors contribute to cultism, peer pressure, inadequate guidance and counselling services, and harmful media exposure had the strongest impact on students' involvement in cult activities.

Table 2: Mean and Rank Order of Social Consequences of Cultism among Students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo State

S/N	The problem of cultism can lead to:	Mean	Rank
9	untimely death of innocent students	3.89	1 st
1	life imprisonment	3.87	2 nd
7	character assassination	3.84	3 rd
3	dent the image of the institution	3.77	4 th
5	increase in crime waves on campus (armed robbery, rape, kidnapping)	3.72	5 th
2	expulsion from school	3.70	6 th
8	destruction of lives and property	3.68	7 th
6	decline in academic performance	3.66	8 th
10	disruption of school academic calendar	3.63	9 th
4	threat to peace and security of life	3.60	10 th

Table 2 showed the mean scores and rank order of the social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic, Oyo State. All the items listed were identified as social consequences of cultism, as their mean scores exceeded the mid-point value of 2.50, indicating

that students recognised them as outcomes of cult-related activities. Although several social consequences were identified, the three most critical were the untimely death of innocent students (mean = 3.89), life imprisonment (mean = 3.87), and character assassination (mean = 3.84), which ranked first, second, and third, respectively. This indicates that while cultism results in many negative social effects, these consequences have the most severe impact on students and the overall campus environment.

Hypothesis One: *There is no significant difference in the causes of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo State based on gender*

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-test Analysis of the Causes of Cultism among Respondents by Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	Cal. t-value	Crit. t-value	p-value
Male	98	53.74	6.38	214	1.35	1.96	0.62
Female	118	52.55	5.89				

* Not significant at 0.05 alpha level

Table 3 showed a calculated t-value of 1.35 and a critical t-value of 1.96. Since the calculated t-value was less than the critical value, the null hypothesis was accepted. This result indicated that there was no significant difference in the causes of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic based on gender. Both male and female students reported similar causes of cultism, suggesting that gender did not play a determining role in the factors that contributed to cultism within the institution.

Hypothesis Two: *There is no significant difference in the social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic in Oyo State based on gender*

Table 4: Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-test Analysis of the Social Consequences of Cultism among Respondents by Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	Cal. t-value	Crit. t-value	p-value
Male	98	65.57	6.53	214	0.76	1.96	0.21
Female	118	64.84	6.74				

* Not significant at 0.05 alpha level

Table 4 indicated a calculated t-value of 0.76 and a critical t-value of 1.96. Since the calculated t-value was less than the critical value, the null hypothesis was accepted. This revealed that there was no significant difference in the social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic based on gender. Both male and female students reported similar social consequences, suggesting that gender did not influence the effects of cultism within the institution.

Discussion

The findings revealed that negative peer influence, inadequate guidance and counselling services, and negative media influence were the major causes of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic. This aligned with Iheanacho et al. (2023), who found that peer pressure, media influence, and lack of counselling contribute to cultism among students. Similarly, Fayokun (2025) identified these same factors as key drivers in tertiary institutions. The reason why respondents

agreed with these findings is that they reflect common realities within the school environment, including the prevalence of peer pressure, insufficient access to guidance services, and exposure to glorified portrayals of cultism in movies, music, and social media. These conditions increase students' vulnerability to cult group recruitment and involvement.

Findings showed that untimely death of innocent students, life imprisonment, and character assassinations were the major social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic. This finding aligned with the study of Adedeji (2022), which revealed that cult-related violence in Nigerian tertiary institutions often leads to fatal clashes, unjust victimisation, and permanent damage to students' reputations. Similarly, Adedeji (2022) observed that students involved in cultism are at high risk of incarceration and social rejection, which negatively affects their future prospects. The respondents might have agreed on these social consequences because of frequent media reports, personal experiences, or testimonies within their academic environment, which reflect the deadly and destructive nature of cult-related activities on campus.

Findings revealed that there was no significant difference in the causes of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic, Oyo State, based on gender. This indicated that male and female students were influenced by similar factors leading to cult involvement. This finding aligned with the study by Ugwu and Chukwuma (2021), which reported that both male and female students in Nigerian tertiary institutions are equally susceptible to peer pressure, negative media influence, and inadequate guidance and counselling, making gender an insignificant factor in cult participation. However, it contradicted Aroyehun (2024), whose study found a significant difference in the causes of cultism among college students based on gender. The lack of significant difference in the present study may be explained by the shared environmental exposures faced by both sexes, including peer group influence, insufficient parental guidance, limited access to counselling services, and pervasive negative media content. These common influences appear to outweigh gender-specific experiences, resulting in a similar pattern of factors driving cult involvement among both male and female students.

Findings also indicated that there was no significant difference in the social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic, Oyo State, based on gender. This indicated that both male and female students experienced the social consequences of cultism in similar ways. This finding aligned with the study by Ugwu and Chukwuma (2021), which reported that the adverse effects of cultism, including academic disruption, psychological trauma, injuries, and social stigma, are experienced equally by male and female students in Nigerian tertiary institutions. However, the result contradicted the findings of Adedeji (2022), who reported that gender determined a significant difference in the consequences of cultism among students of tertiary institutions in Ilorin metropolis. The absence of a significant difference in this study may be explained by the fact that the social consequences of cultism—such as academic disruption, physical harm, expulsion, and loss of life—are often imposed by institutional policies or experienced directly in ways that affect all students, regardless of gender. Exposure to cult-related violence and disciplinary actions tends to impact male and female students in similar ways, creating a shared experience that transcends gender differences.

Conclusion

The study concluded that peer group pressure, inadequate guidance and counselling services, and negative media influence were major causes of cultism, while untimely death of innocent students,

life imprisonment, and character assassination were major social consequences of cultism among students of Ibadan Polytechnic, Ibadan. The study further revealed that there were no significant differences in the causes and social consequences of cultism among students based on gender. Hence, the findings showed that both male and female students share similar views on the causes and social consequences of cultism, making it a common issue among all students. Guidance counsellors, psychologists, school authorities, and education stakeholders can address this through preventive programmes. These include value reorientation, peer counselling, mentorship, and anti-cultism awareness to promote positive behaviour and wellbeing among students.

The findings of the study have implications for school counselling in tertiary institutions. School counsellors must take a proactive role in addressing the root causes of cultism by providing regular guidance programmes that focus on resisting negative peer pressure, promoting moral values, and enhancing media literacy among students. The absence of gender-based differences in the causes and social consequences of cultism suggests that counselling interventions should be inclusive and targeted at the general student population rather than segmented by gender. Counsellors should also collaborate with school authorities to organise sensitisation workshops, offer confidential counselling services for at-risk students, and establish peer mentoring systems to foster positive student interactions. Strengthening the counselling unit within institutions like The Polytechnic, Ibadan, is essential for early identification of students vulnerable to cult influence and for guiding them toward healthier social and academic choices.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that;

1. Students should be empowered by school counsellors, lecturers, and parents through life skills training, mentorship, and counselling to resist negative peer pressure that can lead to cultism while fostering a supportive and inclusive environment.
2. The institution should strengthen guidance and counselling services and implement targeted support and interventions, such as leadership development, peer support groups, and peer education, to reduce students' vulnerability to cultism on campus.
3. School management should educate students through orientation programmes or seminars about the dangers of cultism and its social consequences, including untimely death of innocent students, life imprisonment, character assassination, and disruption of school academic calendar, to prevent its spread on campus.
4. The management of the polytechnic, in collaboration with lecturers and counsellors, should implement prevention programmes that cater to both male and female students, addressing the underlying causes of cultism and promoting a safe and supportive environment.
5. The school should address cultism due to its detrimental consequences on male and female students and foster an inclusive environment that prioritises their well-being and success.

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